

Table 1. Name of Flora, Geographical region and collection period of different Honey samples

Sr. No.	Name of Flora	Region	Collection period
1	Karanj	Maharashtra	Apr.
2	Karvi	Maharashtra, Koyna valley	Oct., Nov.
3	Sunflower	Agriculture area	Aug., Sep., Feb., March and Apr.
4	Mustard	North India, Rajasthan, M.P.	Dec. to Feb.
5	Drumstick	Maharashtra, Bihar	Feb., March
6	Litchi	Himalaya valley, Basins of river Ganga	Apr.
7	Multifloral	collected from various inflorescences in their seasons of various regions.	
8	Eucalyptus	Agriculture region of India	Nov., Dec., Feb. and March
9	Hirda-Gela	Bhima Shankar Valley	Jan. and Feb.
10	Jamun	Sahyadri Valley	Feb. and March
11	Carom seed	Madhya Pradesh, Koyna Valley	Sept. and Oct.

Table 2. Physico-chemical characteristics of honey

Name of Sample	Moisture	Acidity Meq kg ⁻¹	pH	EC mS/cm	Specific gravity	TSS	Ash
Karanj	19.40bc	0.23e	3.63gh	197.93f	1.42de	80.50cd	0.42ab
Karvi	18.50e	0.34a	3.70f	456.33f	1.41e	81.43a	0.41b
Sunflower	19.70b	0.20g	4.04c	477.00a	1.42bc	80.43d	0.42ab
Mustard	19.80ab	0.20g	3.60h	201.93f	1.41f	80.33d	0.42ab
Drumstick	19.76ab	0.26c	3.50g	211.53f	1.42cd	80.3d	0.42b
Litchi	20.17a	0.25c	3.66g	249.7e	1.40g	79.90e	0.42a
Multifloral	19.17cd	0.22f	4.03c	444.00bc	1.42b	80.86e	0.32e
Eucalyptus	19.13cd	0.24d	4.31a	454.67ab	1.43a	80.76bc	0.32ed
Hirda-Gela	19.03cd	0.27b	4.13b	453.43abc	1.43a	80.86b	0.33c
Jamun	19.00cd	0.24d	3.92e	428.47c	1.42cd	80.90b	0.33d
Carom seed	18.87de	0.18h	3.96d	365.47d	1.42bc	81.37a	0.33d
CV	1.36	1.74	0.46	4.13	0.17	0.19	0.97
LSD	0.4451	0.0071	0.0303	25.067	0.0043	0.2669	0.0063

Table 3. Sugar analysis of Honey

Name of Sample	NRS	RS	Fructose	Glucose	F/G
Karanj	7.82e	80.02f	45.39b	34.63de	1.31bc
Karvi	5.29f	79.62gh	43.41cd	36.20c	1.20d
Sunflower	10.17d	79.03i	41.63ef	37.40b	1.11f
Mustard	5.56f	83.97a	46.95a	37.20bc	1.27c
Drumstick	10.2d	83.09b	47.79a	35.30d	1.36ab
Litchi	14.11c	79.85fg	42.53de	37.33b	1.14ef
Multifloral	15.18b	79.38h	40.27g	39.11a	1.03g
Eucalyptus	13.20c	81.42d	44.09c	37.33b	1.18de
Hirda-Gela	13.47c	82.32c	43.20cd	39.12a	1.10f
Jamun	11.02d	81.63d	47.44a	34.19e	1.39a
Carom seed	22.88a	80.47e	40.67fg	39.79a	1.02g
CV	4.99	0.19	1.23	1.37	2.76
LSD	0.99	0.26	0.82	0.86	0.06

Table 4. Nutritional composition of honey

Name of Sample	CHO	Fat	Protein	Fiber	Phenol	Energy (Kcal)
Karanj	79.59cd	0.21ef	0.09c	0.09 cde	16.47ef	321de
Karvi	80.09a	0.55c	0.18abc	0.18 bcd	25.16b	327a
Sunflower	79.23de	0.28e	0.22abc	0.22 abc	17.37def	320e
Mustard	79.22de	0.25e	0.28a	0.28 ab	20.07cde	320.37e
Drumstick	79.32cde	0.17fg	0.27a	0.27 ab	15.58f	320.12e
Litchi	78.84e	0.11g	0.10c	0.10 cde	29.06a	318f
Multifloral	79.34bcd	0.69a	0.26a	0.26 ab	15.28f	325.48ab
Eucalyptus	79.82ab	0.23ef	0.20abc	0.20 abcd	18.57cdef	323.33bc
Hirda-Gela	79.74abc	0.38d	0.12bc	0.12 cde	19.47cde	324.41bc
Jamun	79.45bcd	0.67ab	0.32a	0.32 a	20.97cd	326.02ab
Carom seed	79.70abcd	0.60bc	0.32a	0.32 a	21.57bc	3.26a
CV	0.36	12.33	11.83	40.66	11.49	0.32
LSD	0.99	0.08	0.15	0.126	3.885	1.74

Table 5 Elemental concentrations of honey

Element	Karanj	Karvi	Sunflower	Mustard	Drumstick	Litchi	Multifloral	Eucalyptus	Hirda-Gela	Jamun	Carom seed	CV	LSD
Na(ppm)	389.17ab	3.44abc	335.00bc	211.2c	336.67bc	475.37a	370.23ab	376.39ab	382.54ab	388.70ab	394.86ab	22.24	137.1
K (ppm)	250.40c	1020b	842.10b	337.10c	222.50c	385.80c	1878.30a	1682.90a	1146.30b	1935.80a	922.90b	21.90	358.1
Ca(ppm)	38.55bc	31.58dc	49.08a	37.55bc	28.18d	39.21bc	40.81b	48.88a	42.11ab	44.21ab	37.78bc	11.67	7.86
Fe(ppm)	10.45bcd	13.85a	8.68def	9.05def	7.68f	11.41bc	10.53bcd	9.83cde	11.70bc	12.03b	8.31ef	5.43	1.96
Zn(ppm)	3.78ef	6.45bc	9.23a	2.86f	4.95e	6.66b	5.43bcd	5cde	4.08def	3.41f	9.06a	15.11	1.42
Mg(ppm)	20.33fg	24.61def	39.56a	23.66efg	19.18g	21.46efg	25.36de	36.9ab	29.05cd	32.93bc	24.00def	10.73	4.92
Mn(ppm)	0.93cd	1.70b	2.550a	1.60b	0.31d	0.35d	1.11bc	1.650b	1.38bc	1.00cb	1.26bc	28.57	0.63
Cu(ppm)	0.11f	2.00a	0.35de	0.18f	0.23ef	0.50c	0.50c	0.36d	0.16f	0.15f	0.63b	16.57	0.13
Al(ppb)	400.40bc	871.30b	759.80b	1014.70a	265.60c	339.90bc	400.90bc	745.10abc	805.00abc	1183.40a	1028.60a	47.61	572.77
Ag(ppb)	7.62b	0b	0b	64.12b	142.71a	166.92a	150.21a	24.54b	9.84b	10.26b	18.48b	75.91	69.49
As (ppb)	6.73abcd	2.80cde	4.98abcde	0.74e	1.24e	8.12ab	9.32a	1.23e	2.25ed	3.04bcde	7.72abc	70.66	5.24
Ba (ppb)	184.ab	249.71a	239.5a	90.01c	77.45c	130.29bc	132.9cb	127.42cb	105.06c	129.09bc	85.26c	31.08	74.24
Bi (ppb)	3.62a	0.13b	0.00b	0.00b	0.00b	0.04b	0.00b	0.00b	0.00b	0.00b	0.00b	334.09	1.96
Cs (ppb)	2.91a	1.04c	3.29a	1.36bc	2.86a	2.13abc	2.68a	3.01a	2.75a	2.54ab	2.89a	29.80	1.26
Ga (ppb)	3.18a	2.74ab	1.40bc	1.21c	0.80c	1.02c	0.73c	1.17c	1.41bc	0.85c	1.20c	60.84	1.47
In (ppb)	42.90b	83.37a	39.73c	36.23e	37.57cde	39.06cd	38.07cde	37.00de	37.81cde	36.39e	38.54cde	3.50	2.51
Pb (ppb)	0.313e	51.38a	25.29bc	7.409de	0.556e	12.15de	17.38cd	3.5e	5.938de	0.153e	30.49b	51.45	12.24
Rb (ppb)	63.20ed	904.00ed	2141.70ab	423.00e	843.80ed	1241.20cd	1662.00bc	2727.30a	2330.30a	2685.3a	1734.10bc	22.15	591.95
Se (ppb)	9.07a	5.92abc	4.01abc	0.445c	2.22abc	6.11abc	7.11abc	3.70abc	1.00bc	8.601a	8.466ab	81.48	7.15
Sr (ppb)	259.34ab	153.16bc	337.52ab	286.75ab	59.58c	274.58ab	408.95a	271.41ab	235.97abc	321.58ab	360.02a	41.56	189.94
Ti (ppb)	1889.40ab	24810a	21320a	1441.10bcd	741.20d	1010.20cd	1045.40cd	1731.30bc	1951.80ab	1963.60ab	1652.40bc	26.66	740.44
U (ppb)	4.13a	1.07bc	1.74b	0.28bc	0.32bc	0.98bc	0.47bc	0.35bc	0.00c	0.12c	1.08bc	97.76	1.59
V(ppb)	93.30a	66.19ab	89.84a	5.40c	0.00c	0.00c	0.00c	4.68c	0.00c	3.53c	37.46c	86.25	39.89
Gf(ppb)	1.74a	0.21b	0.07b	0.41b	0.00b	0.00b	0.09b	0.23b	0.36b	0.00b	0.31b	225.99	1.20
Cr(ppb)	5501a	4190a	5356a	878b	196b	182b	410b	265b	245b	169b	247b	97.09	2636.5
Hg(ppb)	123.84a	40.95b	33.98bc	8.46bc	3.70c	2.35c	0.19c	0.10c	0.00c	0.64c	0.00c	105.22	34.69

Table 6. Sensory Attributes

Type of Honey	Colour	Thickness	Flavour	Mouthfeel (Texture)	Taste	Overall Acceptability
Karanj	7.00	7.00	6.80	6.60	7.00	6.88
Karvi	7.40	6.60	7.20	7.60	7.40	7.24
Sunflower	7.60	7.20	7.40	7.60	7.40	7.44
Mustard	6.40	6.40	6.20	6.40	6.60	6.40
Drumstick	7.20	7.40	7.40	8.00	7.20	7.44
Litchi	7.80	7.40	7.80	7.20	8.00	7.64
Multifloral	8.40	9.00	8.60	8.00	9.00	8.60
Eucalyptus	7.60	7.80	8.00	9.00	8.20	8.12
Hirda-Gela	7.80	7.60	8.00	7.80	8.20	7.88
Jamun	8.40	8.20	7.80	7.40	7.60	7.88
Carom seed	7.40	7.00	6.80	6.60	6.60	6.88
CV	9.27	10.16	10.48	10.88	9.57	3.83
LSD	0.95	1.02	1.06	1.10	0.99	0.43